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INTEGRAL HELMINTOSES IN CHILDREN AND THEIR ETIOLOGICAL FACTORS

Abstract: One of the most common diseases today are diseases caused by worms, that is, helminths. 2/3 of the world's population suffers from this disease. Worms find comfortable conditions in the body of young children. Under the influence of worms, the lungs, liver, gall bladder, urinary tract, intestines can become inflamed and even cause ulcers. In addition, it causes a malfunction of the nervous system (a person is overstimulated and sleep is disturbed), anemia (anemia), avitaminosis (a lack of vitamins in the body), a decrease in a person's working capacity, weight loss, and various allergic diseases.

Key words: Helminths, Helminthosis, anemia, Tapeworms, flatworms.

The disease caused by worms, that is, worms, is called Helminthiasis. This disease occurs as a result of young children often not observing cleanliness, eating without washing their hands after playing with various birds, cats, dogs.[1,2,3]

There are 3 different types of worms.

1. Roundworms: ascarida, ostrica, hookworm, intestinal worm, hookworm.
2. Tapeworms, flatworms: cerbar worm, small worm, sucker worm, sucker worm.
3. Extraintestinal worms: trematode, cat tapeworm, liver
dvuustkasi, filaria, schistosomes.[4]

Anti-worms are also divided into 3 types:[5]

1. Nematodes - means used for the treatment of helminthiasis caused by roundworms:
 - Piperazine adipinate 0.2 g in a tablet
 - Naftamon "K" 0.5 g in tablets

- Thymol from 0.5 g in powder
- Dithiazine in powder from 0.1 g
- Difezil from 0.1 in powder
- Pyruvium pamoate from 0.05 g in a dragee
- Pyrantel 0.25 g in tablets
- Levamisole (decaris) 0.15 g in tablets [5]

2. Cestodos - means used for the treatment of helminthosis caused by tapeworms:

- Male fern extract 0.5 g in capsule
- Pumpkin seeds from 130 g
- Aminoacryxin 0.1 g in tablets
- Fenasal in powder from 2.0 g [6]

3. Means used for the treatment of extraintestinal helminthosis:

- Ditrazine citrate 0.1 g in tablets
- Antimonil - sodium tartrate in powder form
- Khloxil in powder from 2.0 g [7]

In addition to the above drugs, the use of medicinal plants also gives effective results in the treatment of worms.[8]

Abu Ali Ibn Sina from the plant of bouymadaran in the removal of worms

used For this purpose, it is recommended to drink 1.5 tbsp. Decoctions of walnut leaves and carrot seeds also have an effective effect on deworming. [9]

In folk medicine:

1. Tincture made from grape leaves and fruit and ripe fruit is used as a medicine for deworming in children.[12]

2. Tincture of mountain jambili is prepared in a ratio of 1:10 and drunk from 1/2 cup for 3 times.[12]

3. Bangidevona plant

4. Garlic tincture

5. Tincture of sedana seeds [10]

Note: The disease is individual in each child, taking into account that, do not forget to consult a doctor before taking any treatment! Parasites will not bother you if you make time for yourself twice a year, consult a doctor, check up and, most importantly, pay attention to the rules of personal hygiene.[11]

Conclusion: When using anthelmintics, the following should be taken into account:

1. It is necessary to pay attention to the diet when taking drugs, because most of the anti-helminthic drugs dissolve in the fat contained in food and lose their properties.
2. It is necessary to use suppositories after taking medicines
3. Sometimes it is required to do an enema before and after taking the medicine
4. Some drugs are drunk on an empty stomach.
5. Of course, before consuming the above drugs, a stool analysis is performed and drugs are recommended with the doctor's advice depending on the type of gelment.
6. Cleanliness and personal hygiene are important for prevention
7. After the worms come off, taking different vitamins will work well.

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